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“THE ROLE OF MICRO FINANCE IN EMPOWERING WOMEN THROUGH ENTREPRENEUSHIP”

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Abstract:

Entrepreneurship as a distinct factor of production contributes to the economic development of an economy. The wide range of significant contributions that entrepreneurship makes to the economic development include promotion of capital formation, creation of immediate large-scale employment, promotion of balanced regional development, effective mobilization of capital and skill, induction of backward and forward linkages and the like. The overall role of entrepreneurship in economic development of an economy is put as "an economy is the effect for which entrepreneurship is the cause." India being one of the largest countries though bestowed with adequate natural resources and human potentials, its development is lopsided. The twin causes, that is, wide inequality between urban and rural.

Micro finance has experiences a dynamic development and today microfinance providers reach close to 100million clients worldwide and are growing fast. This paper will to make an attempt as to present a conceptual paper towards the role of women in India towards empowering the entrepreneurship development through microfinance.

Key words: micro finance, empowerment, entrepreneurship, development ROI etc.,

MICRO FINANCE

Micro Finance is emerging as a powerful instrument for poverty alleviation in the new economy. Micro Finance refers to a collection of banking practices built around providing small loans without any collateral security and accepting tiny deposits. In India, the working of microfinance is more into Self Help Groups (SHGs) aimed at providing a cost-effective mechanism for providing financial services to the “unreached poor”. Based on the philosophy of peer pressure and group savings as collateral substitute, the SHG programme has been successful in not only in meeting the basic needs of the rural poor, but also in strengthening collective self-help capacities of the poor at the local level, leading to their empowerment.

Microfinance Activities

Microfinance includes banking activities where lenders (financial institutions) finance both sellers and buyers for their activities. Commercial Banks invested in projects at large scale while with this, banks invested in consumer finance also. While MFIs usually don’t invest in consumer finance, but give finance only for micro enterprise. MFIs encourage people to lift up their standards by doing businesses and earning from them and this is a consistent and sustainable way. Microfinance is dedicated only to poor and explicitly for business activities. But with this, there are some indirect impacts of microfinance on the micro borrower which are alleviation of poverty, improvement in healthcare, increase in literacy and other social impacts. The following figure gives the detail of microfinance activities by commercial banks and micro finance institutions.

Economic Activity by MFIs

Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship is one of the most widely used term in business, management, economics and other related fields. One of important thing is that entrepreneurship has different meaning for different people, some use it in the meaning of innovation, some use for creativity, risk taking, leadership, and profit maximization or in social context, and some consider it as start up of business, new production methods and many other different meanings. Davidsson, (2004) describes that entrepreneurship is rich phenomenon which makes it a resourceful field. While defining entrepreneurship, we consider some school of thoughts that have major role to define this field. Entrepreneurship, under the flag of Schumpeter school of thought (Swedburg, 2000), is about innovation in organizational process, thinking up new combination, entrepreneurial behavior and motivation of entrepreneurs. While according to Gartner (Thornton,1999), entrepreneurship is about creation of new organization or new startup, creating values and entrepreneur mean owner-manager. In Krizner's view (Swedburg, 2000), entrepreneurship is searching opportunities and exploiting them so it reflects towards the alertness capability of entrepreneur towards profit opportunities. Timmons (Bengtsson, Peterson, 2008) describe different component of entrepreneurship and named it entrepreneurial process. Model emphasizes three entrepreneurial components, Opportunity, Resource and the Team. According to Timmons (Bengtsson, Peterson, 2008) in following fig (4), there is description about each factor which describes best about entrepreneurship and role of entrepreneur is growth of firm:

Timmons entrepreneurial process model (Source: [Bengtsson, Peterson, 2008, p.6](#))

Where there will be more imperfect market there will be more opportunities to exploit. According to Timmons (2008, p.7), "The greater the rate of change, the discontinuities, and the chaos, the greater is the opportunity..." Entrepreneur will have more room to exploit opportunities. So important job is to search opportunities and yield them. This is a core characteristic of entrepreneur that he/she should be opportunistic.

Entrepreneurship development

Entrepreneurship development is seen as one of the important tool to alleviate poverty and reduce gender biases in an economy. As a result, more and more Micro Finance Institutions (MFIs) are providing micro credit to poor people especially women through individual or group lending mechanisms. At the same time by looking at multidimensional and qualitative aspects of poverty, to inculcate entrepreneurship among socio-economically weaker section of women poses a great challenge before any

organization (Mayoux 2001). Few of the organizations like SEWA, Working Women's forum; Annapurna MahilaMandal, etc. have focused their efforts in capacity building of their clients for inculcating entrepreneurship. In general there are two approaches which are followed by MFIs such as minimalist or 'credit only' approach where only credit is provided with the assumption that poor women will use it for economic activity without requiring any additional support and maximalist or 'credit plus' approach where MFIs help women in capacity building through various programmes such as business related training, access to markets, information, networking, etc along with the provision of credit. Today there are more than 24 million households covered directly and another 10 million covered indirectly by microfinance programmes run all over India (Ghate, 2007). The credit made available through microfinance programme is used for variety of purposes by SHG members. Broadly these can be classified in to productive (to set up new business or to expand existing business) and non-productive (consumption loans) uses. One study reveals that around 25 percent of the loans are used for productive purposes to set up entrepreneurial activities, but as the size of average productive loan is higher than that of consumption loan, total 39 percent of loan amount is spent on entrepreneurial activities (Care, MSDF & ICICI Bank, 2008). An another study done by EDA Rural System finds that nearly 63 percent of total credit is used for investment purposes out of which around one third is used for setting new enterprises (EDA Rural Systems Pvt. Ltd. 2005). As discussed, microfinance is a development tool, combination of micro lending with other factors can make possible to alleviate poverty.

Poverty reduction and empowerment of poor model

EMPOWERMENT

Micro credit is used for productive purpose which leads to empowerment but it is necessary to understand the context in which the term 'empowerment' is used. The term 'Empowerment' can be interpreted in different ways as to express self-strength, control, self-power, self-reliance, own choice, life of dignity in accordance with one's values, capable of fighting for one's rights, independence, own decision making, being free, awakening and capacity building. In the broadest sense it means expansion of freedom of choice and action (Narayan, et al., 2002). It also means increasing one's authority and control over the resources and decisions that affect their lives. Kabeer states that empowerment is more closely related to the people who are powerless due to some socio-economic and cultural barriers in the society of which they are part of (Kabeer, 2001). The choices of these powerless people are extremely limited due to lack of resources and lack of better negotiations with the range of formal and informal institutions. Since this powerlessness is embedded in the institutional relations, the empowerment as a concept also needs to be defined in a broader framework. Rolands (1997) defines empowerment as a process whereby women become able to organize themselves to increase their own self-reliance, to assert their independent right to make choices and to control resources which will assist in challenging and eliminating their own subordination (Rolands, 1997). Rolands states that the idea of power is at the root of the term empowerment.

According (Ledgerwood, 2000, pp.1), there are many activities and characteristics are included in microfinance. Some are:

1. Small and short loans
2. Social collateral rather than financial collateral
3. Access to larger amount of loan if payment performance is positive.
4. Search and access the real poor and their business demand
5. Continuous monitoring of business
6. Loan on higher interest rates due expensive financial transactions and risk factor.
7. Easy way to access finance, therefore not too much paper work and easy and short procedures
8. Offering saving services to borrowers even for smallest amount
9. Offer training services to borrower's business development
10. Literacy training to borrowers so that they can come up with competence to daily business problems and its solutions
11. Health care, social services and other skill training services to provide borrower a sustainable base for their business development.

Enterprise Development Services

MFIs, not all, support to borrowers, either in group or individual in different enterprise development services like marketing, business and accounting training etc. This service can be divided in to two parts, enterprise formation and enterprise transformation. In enterprise formation, MFIs provide technical support to group or individual in start up of business, development and maturing ideas and maturing the skills. While, in transformation of enterprise, MFIs arrange trainings for their borrowers, workshops and get together for developing latest skills in their business area (Ledgerwood, 2000).

Women entrepreneurship:

Women's entrepreneurship needs to be studied separately for two main reasons. The first reason is that women's entrepreneurship has been recognized during the last decade as an important untapped source of economic growth. Women entrepreneurs create new jobs for themselves and others and by being different also provide society with different solutions to management, organisation and business problems as well as to the exploitation of entrepreneurial opportunities. However, they still represent a minority of all entrepreneurs. Thus there exists a market failure discriminating against women's possibility to become entrepreneurs and their possibility to become successful entrepreneurs. This market failure needs to be addressed by policy makers so that the economic potential of this group can be fully utilised.

While without a doubt the economic impact of women is substantial, we still lack a reliable picture, describing in detail that specific impact. Recent efforts initiated by the OECD (1997, 2000) are responses to this lack of knowledge and have focused the attention of policy makers and researchers on this important topic. In order to effectively and efficiently address this topic, policy makers need more knowledge about women entrepreneurs. The aim of this report is to extend these efforts and to further enhance knowledge about how women's entrepreneurship affects economic growth and development.

The second reason is that the topic of women in entrepreneurship has been largely neglected both in society in general and in the social sciences (Brush & Hisrich, 1999; Holmquist & Sundin, 2002). Not only have women lower participation rate in entrepreneurship than men but they also generally choose to start and manage firms in different industries than men tend to do (Duchénaut, 1997; Franco & Winqvist, 2002; Reynolds & White, 1997). The industries (primarily retail, education and other service industries) chosen by women are often or have until recently been perceived as being less important to economic development and growth than high-technology and manufacturing. Furthermore, mainstream research, policies and programmes tend to be “men streamer” and too often do not take into account the specific needs of women entrepreneurs and would-be women entrepreneurs. He believes business techniques make not for profit organizations mission go further and faster successfully (Brinherckoff, 2000).

Finally, he describes social entrepreneurship as Stewards (Brinherckoff, 2000), who try new things, serve people in new ways and try to have their organizations be fonts of excellence.

Empowerment and Entrepreneurship:

Powers to the people is the prime mover in the civil liberty. It is the core of self-governance. Empowerment builds self-reliance and strength in women, preparing them towards gathering the ability to determine the choice in life. This adds to the command over resources, out with insubordination and signify their social role. It elevates the strategic gender needs and positions the women in the social strata. It restricts internal oppressions and nips the inequality in the bud.

Drives towards empowerment encourage women for their active interface with socio-economic political events and their fruitful contributions to such episodes as challenging options. Decision making by the women in an empowered state makes them sustainable to withstand any shock of adversity. Slowly, the stability propounded in the sustainable action, makes women to take a bit of innovative effort. She wants to lead than to be led. Schumpeterian ethos that “all enterprises are innovation-led and the entrepreneur is the spark plug of economy” can be practiced by the women group, grooming them through training/development intervention. In this paper, efforts are also made to identify enterprise-specific options to be taken up by activated women self-help group.

Women as entrepreneurs in India:

Women owned businesses are highly increasing in the economies of almost all countries. The hidden entrepreneurial potentials of women have gradually been changing with the growing sensitivity to the role and economic status in the society. Skill, knowledge and adaptability in business are the main reasons for women to emerge into business ventures. ‘Women Entrepreneur’ is a person who accepts challenging role to meet her personal needs and become economically independent. A strong desire to do something positive is an inbuilt quality of entrepreneurial women, who is capable of contributing values in both family and social life. With the advent of media, women are aware of their own traits, rights and also the work situations. The glass ceilings are shattered and women are found indulged in every line of business from pappad to power cables. The challenges and opportunities provided to the women of digital era are growing rapidly that the job seekers are turning into job creators. They are flourishing as designers, interior decorators, exporters, publishers, garment manufacturers and still exploring new avenues of economic participation. In India, although women constitute the majority of the total population, the entrepreneurial world is still a male dominated one. Women in advanced nations are recognized and are more prominent in the business world. But the Indian women entrepreneurs are facing some major constraints like –

a) **Lack of confidence** – In general, women lack confidence in their strength and competence. The family members and the society are reluctant to stand beside their entrepreneurial growth. To a certain extent, this situation is changing among Indian women and yet to face a tremendous change to increase the rate of growth in entrepreneurship.

b) **Socio-cultural barriers** – Women’s family and personal obligations are sometimes a great barrier for succeeding in business career. Only few women are able to manage both home and business efficiently, devoting enough time to perform all their responsibilities in priority.

c) **Market-oriented risks** – Stiff competition in the market and lack of mobility of women make the dependence of women entrepreneurs on middleman indispensable. Many business women find it difficult to capture the market and make their products popular. They are not fully aware of the changing market conditions and hence can effectively utilize the services of media and internet.

d) **Motivational factors** – Self motivation can be realized through a mind set for a successful business, attitude to take up risk and behavior towards the business society by shouldering the social responsibilities. Other factors are family support, Government policies, financial assistance from public and private institutions and also the environment suitable for women to establish business units.

e) **Knowledge in Business Administration** – Women must be educated and trained constantly to acquire the skills and knowledge in all the functional areas of business management. This can facilitate women to excel in decision making process and develop a good business network.

f) **Awareness about the financial assistance** – Various institutions in the financial sector extend their maximum support in the form of incentives, loans, schemes etc. Even then every woman entrepreneur may not be aware of all the assistance provided by the institutions. So the sincere efforts taken towards women entrepreneurs may not reach the entrepreneurs in rural and backward areas.

g) **Exposed to the training programs** - Training programs and workshops for every type of entrepreneur is available through the social and welfare associations, based on duration, skill and the purpose of the training program. Such programs are really useful to new, rural and young entrepreneurs who want to set up a small and medium scale unit on their own.

h) **Identifying the available resources** – Women are hesitant to find out the access to cater their needs in the financial and marketing areas. In spite of the mushrooming growth of associations, institutions, and the schemes from the government side, women are not enterprising and dynamic to optimize the resources in the form of reserves, assets mankind or business volunteers.

Highly educated, technically sound and professionally qualified women should be encouraged for managing their own business, rather than dependent on wage employment outlets. The unexplored talents of young women can be identified, trained and used for various types of industries to increase the productivity in the industrial sector. A desirable environment is necessary for every woman to inculcate entrepreneurial values and involve greatly in business dealings. The additional business opportunities that are recently approaching for women entrepreneurs are Eco-friendly technology, Bio-technology, IT enabled enterprises, Event Management, Tourism industry, Telecommunication, Plastic materials, Vermi culture, Mineral water, Sericulture, Floriculture, Herbal & health care, Food, fruits & vegetable processing.

Conclusion:

Empowering women entrepreneurs is essential for achieving the goals of sustainable development and the bottlenecks hindering their growth must be eradicated to entitle full participation in the business. Apart from training programs, Newsletters, mentoring, trade fairs and exhibitions also can be a source for entrepreneurial development. As a result, the desired outcomes of the business are quickly achieved and more of remunerative business opportunities are found. Henceforth, promoting entrepreneurship among women is certainly a short-cut to rapid economic growth and development. Let us try to eliminate all forms of gender discrimination and thus allow ‘women’ to be an entrepreneur at par with men.

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